

A New Technique for Rapid Middle Ear Muscle Reflex Measurements

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Abstract. Middle-ear muscle reflex (MEMR) thresholds are routinely measured in the audiology clinic. Recent research has shown that MEMR thresholds are elevated in people with evidence of afferent synapse loss despite normal audiometric hearing (i.e., “hidden hearing loss”). Acoustic elicitors are classically presented in a time-consuming fashion that uses discrete steps in sound level and frequency, while a 226 Hz probe tone is used to monitor reflex activation. Clinical and research data efforts could benefit from faster data collection. Moreover, rapid measurements may be less susceptible to slow variations that putatively originate from changes such as probe placement and middle ear pressure. Here, we use our recently developed MEMR measurement paradigm that makes rapid MEMR measurements (2 min test time) with probe clicks and an elicitor noise that continuously sweeps in level. The purpose of this study was 1) to understand the retest reliability of our measurements and 2) to compare results from our paradigm with those obtained using discretely varying elicitors. Thirty young, normal-hearing participants were tested with both the continuous elicitor test (repeated four times) and the discrete elicitor test (tested once). We constructed MEMR level growth functions (LGFs) for each test from sound pressure changes in participants’ ear canals. Using total change, a measure that combines both magnitude and phase changes, LGFs were combined across frequencies from 500-1500 Hz to give a single averaged LGF for each test. Test reliability of the averaged continuous LGFs were assessed using intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC). Most ICC values showed excellent reliability (>0.9). The LGFs from continuous tests were similar to the overall shapes from discrete tests but were larger by an average of 0.4 dB.

INTRODUCTION

The middle ear muscle reflex (MEMR), consisting of the stapedius and tensor tympani muscles, along with associated neural pathways, constitutes a feedback mechanism that modulates middle ear impedance. When activated by moderate to loud sounds, the MEMR results in muscle contractions, increasing middle ear stiffness and resonance. As a result, frequencies below middle ear resonance encounter an increased impedance, resulting in lower transmission into the cochlea. Frequencies above resonance encounter a slightly decreased impedance, resulting in higher transmission into the cochlea. Collectively, activation of the MEMR may reduce the upward spread of masking in the cochlea and may help mitigate the acoustic masking effects of low-frequency background noise.

MEMR tests have been proposed as part of a test battery for differential diagnosis of auditory neuropathy spectrum disorder (Berlin et al., 2005; Valero et al., 2016). Newer wideband techniques have been shown to provide greater test sensitivity to MEMR thresholds (Feeney et al., 2003). Renewed interest in MEMR evaluation has also been sparked by recent discoveries linking MEMR to hidden hearing loss (Liberman et al., 2016; Suthakar & Liberman, 2021). Further gains may be realized by implementing comprehensive MEMR testing methodologies that capture the dynamic nature of the reflex response. We recently developed a novel MEMR test that is relatively quick to administer and captures the dynamics of MEMR growth. Our proposed test uses broadband click probes and a broadband acoustic noise elicitor that continuously sweeps in level. The purpose of this study was 1) to understand the retest reliability of our continuously changing elicitor level paradigm and 2) to compare the results of the continuous paradigm with results from a comparable discrete elicitor level paradigm.

METHODS

MEMR was measured in 30 young, normal-hearing participants. Participants reported not having trouble hearing in quiet or noisy settings. MEMR tests were designed and administered using custom software (Goodman, 2017) written in MATLAB (The MathWorks). Stimuli were presented and recorded using a personal computer and external sound card (Fireface 802, RME, 96 kHz sample rate) connected to a two-channel wideband acoustic probe system (ER-10X, Etymotic Research). Two MEMR paradigms were tested: 1) continuously changing elicitor levels and 2) discrete elicitor levels. The test paradigms are described below. Each participant was tested a total of five times. Continuous elicitor tests were administered twice, followed by a single discrete elicitor test, and then two more continuous elicitor tests. The probes were removed from the participant's ear canals between each test, and a two-minute quiet period was observed. At the start of each test, probes were re-inserted and recalibrated using Thevenin-source methods. The continuous elicitor test took two minutes to run, while the discrete elicitor test took 12 minutes. The total test time for each participant was approximately 30 minutes.

Continuously Changing Elicitor Levels. MEMR was measured using a train of broadband clicks (96 dB pSPL at a rate of 20/s) in the ipsilateral (left) ear and a broadband noise elicitor in the contralateral (right) ear. The noise elicitor swept upwards in level from 40 to 110 dB SPL in four seconds, then downwards from 110 to 40 dB SPL in four seconds (rate of 17.5 dB/s). A single sweep therefore lasted eight seconds, during which 160 clicks were presented. Fifteen sweeps comprised one test, so each test was two minutes long. The MEMR level growth function (LGF) (i.e., the change in ear canal sound pressure as a function of elicitor level) resulting from this procedure had a resolution of one click per 0.875 dB of elicitor change (17.5 dB/s elicitor change measured with 20 clicks/s).

Discrete Elicitor Levels. MEMR was measured using a single broadband click (96 dB pSPL) in the ipsilateral ear, followed by a 500 ms broadband noise elicitor in the contralateral ear and then a second click in the ipsilateral ear, followed by 1 s of silence. This sequence was repeated 12 times for each elicitor level. Elicitor levels increased from 37.5 to 92.5 dB SPL in 5 dB steps and then decreased from 90 back to 35 dB SPL. The total test time was 12 min. This paradigm is similar to tests described by (Keefe et al., 2010) and (Mepani et al., 2020). The LGF from this procedure had a resolution of one click per 5 dB of elicitor change.

Analysis

Recorded clicks were time windowed using a flattop window 13 ms in total length, including 143 μ s raised cosine onset and offset ramps. The start of the window was at the peak of the recorded clicks, so that the onset ramp removed most of the initial (incident) peak energy of the click, leaving the portions of the pressure waveforms containing predominantly reflected energy (including multiple internal reflections between the probe tip and eardrum). Windowed clicks were zero-padded and Fast Fourier Transformed to yield 100-Hz wide analysis bins. Eleven FFT bins centered at frequencies from 500-1500 Hz were selected for further analysis.

Because this study focused on MEMR dynamics occurring across 8-second intervals, slower changes were removed by a detrending operation. Detrending was applied separately to each frequency. In the frequency domain, the complex values were arranged in a time series, and a weighted smoothing spline was fit to the series and then subtracted to remove slow changes. The weights for the spline were given a value of one, except for noisy samples, which were given a weight of zero. Noisy samples were determined using a quartile-based method of determining outliers. Detrending was applied separately to the real and imaginary parts. For the continuous test, the detrending was applied across a 2-minute series of 2,400 clicks (160 clicks per sweep x 15 sweeps). For the discrete test, the detrending was applied across an 18-second series of 12 clicks, and the detrending was applied separately for clicks occurring before and after the noise elicitor.

After detrending, the data were arranged to form (complex) LGFs and averaged across repeated presentations (15 sweeps for the continuous paradigm and 12 presentations for the discrete paradigm). The mean LGFs were lowpass filtered using smoothing splines (performed separately for the real and imaginary parts). The smoothed LGFs were then normalized by dividing by (complex) baseline measurements. This normalization expressed LGFs as the ratio magnitude change and the difference phase change. For the continuous paradigm, baseline was the average of the first three and last three click responses. For the discrete paradigm, each click response in the LGF had its own baseline (the averaged click responses presented before each noise elicitor were the baseline for the averaged click responses following the noise elicitor).

RESULTS

Initially, the complex MEMR LGFs were considered in terms of magnitude change only. As shown in Fig. 1A, at frequencies below middle ear resonance (e.g., 500 Hz), activation of the MEMR led to an increase in ear canal SPL, consistent with stiffening of the ossicular chain, an upward shift in middle ear resonant frequency, and increased middle ear impedances at these frequencies. Conversely, at frequencies above middle ear resonance (e.g., 1500 Hz), activation of the MEMR led to a decrease in ear canal SPL, also consistent with an upward shift in middle ear resonant frequency and reduced middle ear impedances at these frequencies.

At frequencies near middle ear resonance (typically between 800-1200 Hz), LGFs showed non-monotonic growth patterns in response to strictly increasing (i.e., 40-110 dB SPL) or decreasing (i.e., 110-40 dB SPL) elicitor levels (Fig. 1A, red and blue lines).

FIGURE 1. Relative magnitude changes in ear canal pressure as a function of elicitor level and time. **Panel A:** Data from one participant. Each trace shows the response at one frequency. Two frequencies exhibiting non-monotonic growth are shown in red and blue. Three discrete points in the LGF are marked and applied to a conceptual model in Panel B. **Panel B:** A simple bandpass model of middle ear admittance predicts the frequency-specific growth patterns observed. As elicitor level increases, the MEMR exerts a stronger stapedius muscle contraction, increasing the stiffness and shifting the resonance to higher frequencies. For frequencies either below or well above baseline resonance (gray vertical arrows), growth is monotonic. For frequencies slightly above baseline resonance (red and blue vertical arrows), growth is non-monotonic, and can sometimes cross zero (red arrow, point 3).

reported at adjacent elicitor levels. If the LGFs were monotonic, averaging across frequencies would avoid this problem, and the averaging could provide further noise reduction. It is therefore of interest to consider whether phase information might also be usefully incorporated into measures of MEMR activation.

Joint magnitude and phase changes can be visualized by plotting LGFs in the complex plane (Fig. 2A). Each set of “pinwheel arms” represents a single frequency. Each frequency trace moves from baseline (no change) at the point $1+0i$ on the complex plane to some extrema as the elicitor increases and then back to baseline as the elicitor decreases. Places where the movement away and back to baseline do not overlap are indicative of MEMR hysteresis. Examination of Panel 2A shows how the phase curvature with changes in MEMR-induced stiffness leads to non-monotonic magnitude growth for frequencies that first move towards the origin and then back towards the unit circle. Importantly, the lengths of the traces for each frequency are quite similar, suggesting that if the lengths of the traces were computed via complex integration, the responses of all frequencies might show similar growth patterns, conducive to subsequent averaging to obtain a single mean LGF. The lengths of each trace can be found by $\int k\sqrt{(dx/dt)^2 + (dy/dt)^2} dt$, where x and y are the real and imaginary parts of the complex LGF, respectively, t is the corresponding time vector, and k is assigned a value of +1 when the stiffness is increasing and -1 when the stiffness is decreasing. A nearly identical result can be obtained more simply by subtracting 1 from the complex LGF and then computing magnitude:

1A, red and blue lines). Such non-monotonic magnitude changes are consistent with shifting middle ear resonance due to increasing MEMR-induced stiffness. Figure 1B illustrates this with a conceptual model of middle ear admittance as a simple bandpass filter shape. Three different elicitor levels in the LGF (1, 2, and 3) are considered at four frequencies (shown by vertical arrows). As middle ear stiffness increases, the resonance shifts to higher frequencies, resulting in changing amounts of reflected sound at each frequency, as shown by the lengths of the red, blue, and gray arrows.

Standard clinical measurements in adults utilize a 226 Hz probe tone to detect MEMR, and non-monotonic LGFs would not be expected for such a low frequency. However, previous work (Feeney et al., 2003; Feeney & Sanford, 2005) has suggested that wideband measures of MEMR are more sensitive indicators of threshold than single frequencies. This raises a potential problem, in that certain frequencies can show non-monotonic magnitude growth, leading to apparent decreasing responses as the elicitor increases. If the largest response is chosen at any given elicitor level, this could lead to apparent “jumps” or distortions of the LGF slope as the magnitudes of different frequencies are

$\sqrt{(x - 1)^2 + y^2}$. This operation shifts the baseline of the LGF to the origin before computing magnitude, so that both magnitude and phase are combined into the resulting value. We therefore refer to this measure as “total change”. Figure 2B shows the LGFs obtained when expressed as total change. Compared to magnitude change alone (Fig. 1A), total change is less variable across frequency. We therefore computed the mean total change across all 11 frequencies to obtain a single, averaged LGF for each test (black dots in Fig 2C).

As shown by arrows and labels in Fig. 2C, averaged LGFs were described by five measures. *Maximum total change* was the largest change that occurred in the LGF. *Onset delay* was the difference between the time at which the

FIGURE 2. **Panel A:** Complex changes in ear canal pressure as a function of elicitor level (same participant as in Fig. 1). A portion of the unit circle is shown in black. Data points that fall on the unit circle have no magnitude change. Data points falling inside the circle show a magnitude decrease, while points falling outside the circle show a magnitude increase. Data points falling at zero on the y-axis have no phase change. Data points rotated above zero have a phase lead, while points rotated below zero have a phase lag. **Panel B:** LGFs expressed as total change. Compare to magnitude change only in Fig. 1A. **Panel C:** Measures used to quantify averaged total change LGFs.

maximum elicitor level was presented (4 s) and the time at which the maximum total change was observed. This value was typically in the 100-200 ms range, consistent with reported MEMR reflex delays (Møller, 1958). Because the noise floor itself is a variable estimate, and because we found that noise floors sometimes fluctuated across repeated tests, thresholds were defined using a criterion level of the maximum total change minus 12 dB. The elicitor levels at which this amount of total change was achieved, (after shifting the function to account for reflex delay), were taken as the *onset and offset thresholds*. *Hysteresis* (in dB) was quantified as offset threshold minus onset threshold.

Continuous Elicitor Retest Reliability

Four repeated continuous elicitor tests were made from each of the 30 participants. All participants had LGFs consistent with a present MEMR response. Median values were 2.07 dB for maximum total change, 210 ms for onset delay, 86.92 dB SPL for onset threshold, 71.19 dB SPL for offset threshold, and -15.36 dB for hysteresis. Despite all participants having normal hearing status, considerable variability was observed across individuals. For example, maximum total change ranged from 0.16 to 10.51 dB. The repeatability of the continuous elicitor test for the five LGF-derived measures was quantified using intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC, type ‘C-k’, (McGraw & Wong, 1996)). ICCs demonstrated excellent repeatability for maximum total change (0.96), onset thresholds (0.96), offset thresholds (0.97), and hysteresis (0.94), while good repeatability was found for onset delay (0.85). Taken together, these results indicate that continuous LGFs yield highly consistent results across repeated administrations within individuals.

LGFs from Continuous versus Discrete Elicitors

Overall, LGFs obtained with the discrete test were similar in shape to those obtained using the continuous test (Fig. 3, top row). Because the discrete test did not include elicitor levels greater than 92.5 dB SPL, direct comparisons were not possible at the highest elicitor levels used in the continuous test. While the continuous test provided a measure of reflex delay, the discrete paradigm did not. To aid comparisons, the continuous LGFs in Fig. 3 have been appropriately shifted along the x-axis to account for reflex delay. Two thirds of participants (20/30) had results similar to those shown in the top row. One third of participants did not show an MEMR response on the discrete test. Representative examples of this no-response group are shown in the bottom panel of Fig. 3. Note that the continuous

LGRs for these participants are more sharply peaked than those in the top panel. It seems likely that these participants would have shown discrete MEMR responses, had higher elicitor levels been used for the discrete test.

Direct comparisons between test results obtained at the lowest elicitor levels equate to simply comparing noise floor estimates of the two tests. To ensure a meaningful comparison of LGFs, quantitative differences were

FIGURE 3. Comparison of LGFs obtained with continuous and discrete elicitor tests. Each panel shows results from one participant. Continuous results are shown by solid lines. The four continuous tests are shown by thin gray lines, and the median of the four tests is shown by a thicker red line. Results of the discrete test are shown by blue lines and circle markers. The break in the discrete test near the center of each panel is from the highest elicitors not being tested in the discrete paradigm. Vertical dashed lines show onset and offset thresholds for the continuous test. **Top Row:** Two thirds of participants had results similar to these examples. **Bottom Row:** One third of participants did not show results consistent with a present MEMR when tested with the discrete method, though their continuous results clearly showed the presence of MEMR.

considered only at discrete elicitor levels which were greater than or equal to the continuous thresholds of each participant. These comparison points are those shown by the blue circles that are inside the pairs vertical dashed lines in each panel. Figure 4 shows the dB differences between LGFs obtained with the two methods. Differences were similar across elicitor levels, with the continuous LGFs being 0.41 dB larger on average ($SD = 0.70$ dB).

DISCUSSION

Though they tended to show qualitatively similar LGF shapes, the continuous elicitor test yielded total change values that were 0.41 dB larger. The reason for this difference is unknown, but one explanation might be the cumulative effect of the continuously modulated elicitor for two minutes with no intervening silent periods. In contrast, the discrete method had one second of silence after each trial. The larger amount of change observed for the continuous test may be advantageous in producing a better signal-to-noise ratio, increasing reflex detectability. A substantial proportion of normal hearing participants (1/3) did not show an MEMR response to the discrete test. A likely reason for this discrepancy is that the discrete test did not use high enough elicitor levels.

In this paper, we suggest a new measure of MEMR activation, total change, which integrates both magnitude and phase changes into a single measure. Total change removes the non-monotonic growth from the LGFs of frequencies near middle ear resonance. Use of total change results in the LGFs of different frequencies being similar, so that they can be averaged into a single mean LGF. It has been suggested that wideband measures result in more sensitive MEMR tests. We compared ICC values obtained using the magnitude only of a single LGF centered at 200 Hz with ICC values obtained using the total change averaged across 11 frequencies from 500-1500 Hz. In all cases, the ICCs obtained

FIGURE 4. Differences in total change for continuous versus discrete elicitor tests. Values from the discrete test were subtracted from corresponding continuous median values. Data points used for comparison were those at discrete elicitor levels \geq the continuous onset and offset thresholds for each of the 20 participants that showed a response to MEMR in the discrete test. The number of participants contributing to the box and whisker plots at each level are shown along the top of the figure.

using averaged total change were higher, supporting the use of averaged total change in characterizing MEMR.

The continuous elicitor test showed good to excellent repeatability across all five quantitative measures describing the LGFs. The high ICC values suggest

that the continuous test is highly repeatable for a given individual, at least within a single lab visit. The retest variability would likely increase when waiting longer periods of time between tests; however, these initial results are encouraging and may prompt further exploration regarding the usefulness of this test. In standard clinical measurements, only MEMR onset threshold is considered. The continuous elicitor test can provide additional reliable estimates of MEMR dynamics, including maximum total change, reflex delay, offset threshold, and hysteresis. It remains to be seen whether these measures may be usefully correlated with other aspects hearing health.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION\

[Susan Voss]: Figure 2 and the representation of growth functions in the complex plane is really neat. I don't have intuition as to why the total change (Fig 2B) is monotonic for all frequencies or why the growth is largest at frequencies 1100 and 1200 Hz (red and blue) whereas the magnitude change was smallest at these frequencies. At the same time, I can appreciate that this measure in Figure 2B is useful and includes both phase and magnitude components.

[Authors' Response]: This is a good question. One way to intuit this is by considering that theoretically, as the MEMR activator increases, the stapedius muscle pulls harder in a nonlinear but monotonic way. If this is true, then a measure describing MEMR activation should behave in the same way. Total change can be thought of as the accumulating length of the complex curve for each frequency as it moves away from baseline to its furthest extent. Lengths are always positive, so they accumulate monotonically. When calculated this way, the total change tends to be largest where the phase rotates rapidly (near middle ear resonance), even though corresponding magnitude changes are small. This is because small changes in phase are equivalent to relatively large changes in magnitude. It may help to consider that total change is similar to root-mean-square change. If two sinusoids are subtracted and the RMS difference is computed, small phase changes give the same RMS difference as larger magnitude changes. For example, a 2 dB magnitude change is equivalent to a 0.2596 radian change (~0.04 cycles). This relationship is quantified and explored more fully in a recent publication (Goodman, Haysley, and Jennings, 2024; JARO).

[Susan Voss]: I had trouble figuring out the definitions for onset and offset thresholds – how do we see a change in 12 dB? Or is this just the elicitor level at which the response is 12 dB above a noise floor that is not shown in the figure? This could be made clearer perhaps.

[Authors' Response]: Thank you for pointing out the need for greater clarity on this point. We considered a few different ways of quantifying “threshold”. One way, which you noted, is to find where the signal rises above the noise floor by some criterion amount. One disadvantage of this method is that the noise floors, as well as their estimates, can vary across repeated tests. Additionally, the signal becomes more variable as it approaches the noise floor and is more influenced by the noise. The method we used was to find the point at which the peak (the maximum total change) was reduced by 12 dB, and then find where the curve crossed that line. This has some similarities to part of the procedure for determining the Q or Q10 value for filter bandwidth or neural tuning curves. The number 12 was chosen because empirically, it gave the most repeatable results.

[Susan Voss]: Why was the individual subject whose results were plotted in Fig. 1 and 2 chosen? Was this a typical response or was it one of the more clean and clearer examples? Perhaps the poster will show more examples but some description of where it fits in the population of 30 subjects would be helpful. Also, can you help us understand more qualitatively (maybe with a figure of repeated measures, beyond the summary statistics) how repeatable these measurements were on a given subject? Perhaps on the example subject?

[Authors' Response]: The data from the individual subject shown were chosen because they were a clear and representative example from the larger set of 30 subjects. We agree that more examples should be plotted to show the range of responses obtained. We did not include such plots here due to space limitations; however, we will include them in the full paper we are preparing. We also agree that summary statistics, such as the ICC, are of limited use in understanding how many dB different each measurement is expected to be. We did not include such plots here due to space limitations but will include them in the full paper.

[Irina Wils]:

Could you give some more information on the broadband clicks that were used? For example, what is their fast Fourier transformation?

[Authors' Response]: The clicks were calibrated in each individual ear to give a flat forward pressure level (FPL) spectrum at the eardrum. Previous work in our lab suggests that our techniques achieve accuracy of +3 dB from 100 Hz to 20 kHz. While the forward stimulus pressure is flat at the eardrum, the SPL measured by the microphone at the entrance of the ear canal (and subsequently used for data analysis) is a combination of forward and reverse pressures. The SPL spectrum is therefore not flat and has peaks and valleys due to ear canal resonances.

[Irina Wils]: Could you specify why bins centered at frequencies from 500-1500 Hz were selected for the analysis?

[Authors' Response]: We chose this frequency range because we hypothesized, they would provide the most stable and repeatable results. Lower frequencies show larger magnitude changes in response to MEMR; however, the biological noise floor also rises quickly as frequency falls below 500 Hz, leading to poor SNR and increased variability. At higher frequencies, MEMR-induced changes become smaller, again leading to a poor SNR and increased variability. The range we tested was able to detect small but repeatable changes. That said, we did not try to determine the definitive set of “best” cutoff frequencies, and further research may suggest slight adjustments to these cutoffs

[Irina Wils]: I think it would be interesting to visualize the total change of all 30 participants. Are you able to share that data?

[Authors' Response]: We agree that this is important information to share. Due to space limitations, we cannot include it here; however, we will certainly show this data in the full paper. The variability across participants was quite large, while the variability across repeated tests was much smaller.

[Gabrielle Merchant]: This method differs from clinical MEMR protocols (which pressurize the ear canal and look at changes in admittance or compliance) versus changes in ear canal SPL. Might be helpful to make those differences clearer to readers who might be more familiar with "traditional" MEMRs.

[Authors' Response]: Thank you for this helpful suggestion. We will include a discussion of this important point in the full paper. We expect that our unpressurized measurements will be slightly smaller than measurements made in ear canals with equalized pressures; however, for individuals with normal middle ears, the differences should be slight. It would be interesting to implement our test in a device that can pressurize the canal and compare the results. In terms of measurement quantities, we examined the LGFs when quantified as forward pressure, reverse pressure, pressure reflectance, and power reflectance. We found the results were similar, except for power reflectance, which discards the phase information, leading to nonmonotonic changes near resonance.